

ISic0762

I.Sicily inscription 0762

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Vito Soldano di Canicatti, 1972

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]sacr(um)(vac.undefin)□
2. [---]statum dei cum
3. [---]fec(it)

Apparatus

Preliminary text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175798

EDCS 6100291

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0345a

De Miro, E., Fiorentini, G. 1972-1973. Attività della Soprintendenza alle antichità della Sicilia centro-meridionale negli anni 1968-72. *Kokalos*. 18-19: 228-250. At 247 tav.62 fig.4

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 188 no.75 fig.80

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